

MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

Final Conference

MATILDE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 870831

MATILDE

Migration ImpAct assessment To Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European rural and mountain regions

Final Conference

Call: H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2019

Work Programmes:

H2020-EU.3.6.1.1. The mechanisms to promote smart, sustainable and inclusive growth

H2020-EU.3.6.1.2. Trusted organisations, practices, services and policies that are necessary to build resilient, inclusive, participatory, open and creative societies in Europe, in particular taking into account migration, integration and demographic change

Deliverable 7.6

Final Conference in Brussels

Author(s):

Alicja Fajfer, Marika Gruber, Kristijan Miksche

Cover photograph: Vanina Ninova

Approved by Project Coordinator: Jussi Laine, UEF (2.1.2023)

Version: 2.1.2023

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7467473

How to cite: MATILDE (2022). Final Conference. Deliverable 7.6 [online] Available at:
<https://matilde-migration.eu>

This document was produced under the terms and conditions of Grant Agreement No. 870831 for the European Commission. It does not necessarily reflect the view of the European Union and in no way anticipates the Commission's future policy in this area.

Table of Contents

The Conference Idea..... 2

 Main Message..... 4

 Conference in Photos 7

Local impact..... 10

Media coverage 14

Program 15

Gender balance 19

The Conference Idea

Photo 1 MATILDE team at the final conference. ©Kathrin Zupan

The MATILDE final conference was organized as a **2-day event, on 10-11 November 2022 in Villach, Austria**. The University of Eastern Finland co-organized the conference in close collaboration with the Carinthia University of Applied Sciences (CUAS) and the City of Villach. Day 1 was held at the Congress Centre, whereas Day 2 was held at the CUAS campus.

This conference presented and promoted the cross-country findings of the MATILDE project, inviting European stakeholders and policy makers to join the initiative. The event created a discussion platform for the MATILDE researchers and local partners, and international experts representing different stakeholder and policy levels, from local to the EU. In addition to the representatives from DG Agri and DG Home, the discussion was joined by participants from various NGOs and think-tanks on migration, local and rural development fields,

representatives of the key international organizations such as IOM, UNHCR, as well as journalists. Prominent scholars from outside the project were invited to critically challenge and/or validate the presented project insights. The event provided a space to improve the dialogue between social scientists, policymakers, and various social and economic milieus in order to provide better responses to the challenges posed by migration and integration governance. The key findings and policy recommendations that emerged from the experimentation were debated together, and the participants were encouraged to explore the resources produced by the project.

The event gathered **299 participants** from all over Europe, but also further away, on both days, which exceeded our expectations. For **better accessibility**, the event was organized in a **hybrid** mode. English-to-German **interpretation** was provided on Day 1, and German-to-English interpretation was provided on Day 2. The event was also featured in German and Austrian national news, and the debate continued intensively in many social media platforms.

Given the very positive feedback received from the participants, we are proud to consider the event to have been a great success and fuelled connections and other forms of impact that will last beyond the mere project frame. The high interest and participation levels can be taken as a testimony of the relevance of the topic at hand. The high level of participation was also a relief to the organizers, who took a conscious, yet calculated risk in moving the final event outside its originally planned location, Brussels, in an attempt to highlight the development potential of the European rural and mountain regions in examining how migration impacts on local development and territorial and cohesion in today's Europe.

As MATILDE focuses on the social and economic impacts of migration in rural and mountainous areas, we considered it as necessary to organize our final conference in a setting that would be pertinent to our research aims and scope. CUAS had planned to have a final project event in the case study region of Villach and proposed to change this event

into a 2-day MATILDE conference. Villach fulfils the framework conditions that MATILDE has been dealing with. The Villach-Klagenfurt region is more than 50 percent covered by mountains and more than 50 percent of the population lives in a mountain area. In general, almost 94 percent of the municipalities in Carinthia can be classified as “rural” according to the European Urban-Rural Classification. The city of Villach not only has a long historical tradition of immigration, but also lies at the intersection of three cultures in the Alps-Adria region. Villach was also the first municipality (and so far the only one) which developed an integration model in the province of Carinthia.

Photo 2 The final conference was moved to the alpine town of Villach. ©Lauri Havukainen

Main Message

MATILDE examines rural, often remote, areas which are affected by unemployment, lower education levels of the inhabitants and a general population decline or stagnation. The analysis conducted shows that migrants contribute to maintain alive local economies, to enlarge the offer in local markets, and their presence trigger innovations. Nevertheless, the analysis also found that while contributing to sustain local economies migrants often experience exploitation under various forms: notably poor legal work conditions and informal work, long working hours and intensive labour, low wages, informal housing in the workplace. At the same time, the policy analysis shows that in many MATILDE

countries, migration and/or integration regulations have been tightened, especially since the “refugee crisis”. In many countries, we can find that while there is a shortage of skilled workers or a decline in working-age population, at the same time potential workers (asylum seekers) are excluded by law from the labour market. Furthermore, while some countries and regions are dependent on immigration (e.g. in terms of labour demand and population development), and migrants often have to take up jobs that are poorly paid, precarious and not accepted by the local population, many migrants in rural areas have to experience discrimination, racism, exclusion and discrimination.

The MATILDE reports also show that different types of migrants are treated differently: Laws and policies explicitly and implicitly categorise immigrants as ‘wanted’ and ‘unwanted’ immigrants, or as immigrants ‘in need of integration’ and immigrants who are ‘already integrated’ or ‘beyond integration’. The reports on the social and economic impacts of migrants/TCNs on rural regions clearly show that migration to rural areas provides a chance to revitalize the regions (e.g. mitigating population loss, maintaining local supply and important services through migrant business start-ups and staff provision, maintaining schools or cultural offerings). In order to benefit from the positive impacts that migration can have on rural areas, it is necessary to increase the participation possibilities of migrants in local society and local structures and to change the negative perception of immigrants, particularly refugees, by locals.

Key pointers:

- When defining strategies and policies, it is not enough to look at countries, it is the regional level that brings out the important disparities, opportunities and challenges.
- Rural regions face many challenges, such as population loss and a shrinking share of working-age population, lower educational levels, higher unemployment rates, thinning out of infrastructure with simultaneous need for local supply and services (e.g. care, education, public transport).

- The development of rural regions also depends on external factors such as migration movements, which in turn are controlled by national laws.
- Immigration, both qualified and less-qualified, can contribute to the revitalization of rural, shrinking regions, but needs legal provisions that does not make unnecessary distinctions and where certain origins, cultures, religions, languages lead to fewer opportunities. Legal regulations should be formulated in such a way that they are non-discriminatory, free of racism and do not divide society. Rather, they should open up recognition, opportunities for participation and be demanded from state as well as private actors. Furthermore, it should be insisted that member countries do not fall behind the EU's integration policy goals and create a narrower legal framework that may even contradict EU laws.
- Thus, policies addressing region's and TCN needs have to reflect properly their diversity.
- A policy is needed that values and promotes rural areas and their resources; not only promotion of urban centres, do not leave rural areas behind.
- Enhance remote and rural regions' attractiveness and favour migrants' permanent or long-term settlement; therefore, policies need to address migrant essential needs (i.e. proper housing facilities, fast access to the labour market, participation, and social inclusion opportunities; promote equal rights for locals and migrants, in terms of access to services, social inclusion, labour market access, which can also foster the cohesion of the territories).
- This also needs a strengthening of rural/mountainous regions' resilience by strengthening local/regional self-awareness through proper self-assessment tools, considering i.e. the people living there, migration flows, labour market needs or demographic developments.

Conference in Photos

Photo 3 On both days, the conference gathered almost 300 participants, including researchers, practitioners and policy makers. ©Per Olav Lund

Photo 4 Jussi P. Laine, MATILDE Coordinator, introduces the project. ©Per Olav Lund

Photo 5 Gerda Sandriesser, the Deputy Mayor of Villach, welcomes the participants. ©Gözde Kazaz

Photo 6 MATILDE researcher Maria Luisa Caputo presents findings.

©Per Olav Lund

Photo 7 MATILDE researcher Ayhan Kaya presents the Turkish case study. ©Gözde Kazaz

Photo 8 Hybrid panel discussion: challenges, changes and chances of and through migration. ©Gözde Kazaz

Photo 9 Christopher Hofbeck and Alessia Felin, both from Caritas Bolzano, present action research activities in their region. ©Caritaz Bolzano

Photo 10 Policy roundtable with representatives of local, national and European stakeholders. ©Lauri Havukainen

Photo 11 On Day 2 the conference activities continued at the CUAS campus, and in the German language. ©Lauri Havukainen

Local impact

In addition to the broad project wide impact, for CUAS, our local organiser, the conference was a good opportunity to bring local, regional, national and European policy makers, scientists and further public and private stakeholders together and to foster its position as strong research partner and a local project conference organiser in an international project environment. The conference also helped CUAS to further extend the network with key international academics, practitioners, and policy makers.

For CUAS, the conference was also an opportunity to create further awareness in Carinthia and Austria for the topics of migration, integration and demographic change, which are ongoing future topics and will continue to accompany societies. The conference was also able to show how extensive and directly applicable results research projects bring to the municipalities, regions and countries, which also confirms the eligibility for funding and makes clear the further need for research and research funding in this research area.

The event would have not been possible without the strong support from the City of Villach, a local partner in the MATILDE project. The event was of great interest to the city as the realm of integration work and integration policy are being currently developed in the City of Villach and in the surrounding region of Carinthia, one of the case study regions of the project. Villach put itself once again on the map of places and cities, where migration and integration are increasingly considered central topics for the development and cohesion of society. Having the conference in Villach/Carinthia was an important move as it helped to re-introduce the topic to the public and political discourse in the region, and now in a different light than in the past. While much of the media coverage about migration, asylum seekers and the inability/unwillingness of regional and other authorities to create enough accommodation for refugees has been rather negative or sensationalist, the event managed to add a voice of reason and rationality supported by researched actualities and success stories. The media coverage about this kind of approach towards those topics was very positive.

The City of Villach reports that that they can already see an effect stemming from the conference in terms of increasing awareness about migration/integration. Many of the key data had not easily explicable to decision makers and the related possibilities and responsibilities particularly for the local authorities and administration had been unclear. Due to the nearly yearlong campaign before the conference and the conference itself, there is a perceptible shift in the approach towards the topic. Concretely, events, organization of which were not yet politically possible in the near past, will now be possible. For example, while the horizontal coherency within the migration affairs between different levels of

governance was lacking before, the dialogue kick started at the MATILDE conference paved the way for further and better-informed multilevel collaboration towards a more holistic and realistic perspective about migration and integration

The two-day conference was participated by representatives from all stakeholder groups identified in the MATILDE Stakeholder Involvement Plan (D2.8).

Photo 12 The ‘Interculturality in Practice’ session was an opportunity for local partners and other local organizations to present their work and network. ©Vanina Ninova

The following overview shows a selection of local and regional stakeholders in Carinthia: Associations and Clubs (e.g., Arabic women association “Arabesc”), Asylum and refugee care (e.g., Diakonie de La Tour, Wernberg Monastery, Refugee and Integration Department of the Province of Carinthia), Academia (different research facilities and individual researchers as well as bachelor, master and PhD-students; in total scholars from 24 universities and research facilities participated), Education and training institutions (universities, adult education centres Carinthia, i.e. Bildungswerk Kärnten), Internal stakeholders (i.e. MATILDE supporters such as the Kärntner Gemeindebund, Land Kärnten, IOM, Alliance in the Alps, Euromontana), International umbrella organizations (e.g., Alliance in the Alps, IOM International, Mountain Research Initiative, OECD, European Network for Rural Development-ENRD), Local partners of Carinthia and Vorarlberg (e.g., different departments of the city of Villach as well as policy makers of Villach and the province of Carinthia; okay.zusammen leben, REGIO Klostertal-Arlberg), NGOs (e.g., Carinthian International Centre,

Projektgruppe Frauen, Willkommen Nachbarn, Platform Migration Carinthia, Migrantinnenberatung Spittal, Caritas, Diakonie de la Tour), Non-organized/other interest groups (several migrants and volunteers), Political decision makers ([former] mayor, city councillor of Villach, District Governor Klagenfurt Land, President of the Carinthian Parliament), Private Businesses (e.g., business consultants, migrant entrepreneurs in Carinthia), Public administrations (local, regional, national and European levels, e.g.: integration commissioner of the city of Villach, women's officer of the City of Villach, Social Welfare Department of the City of Villach, integration commissioner of the province of Carinthia, Carinthian State Office for Statistics, Carinthian State Office for Refugees, Ombud for Equal Treatment Carinthia, Carinthian State Office for the strategic land development, Carinthian Welcome Center, Carinthian Regional Manager, REGIO Klostertal-Arlberg, County Board Dalarna, Federal Ministry for European and International Affairs, Austrian Integration Fund, European Commission – DG AGR” and DG HOME), Public welfare service providers (e.g., Labour Market Service Carinthia), Trade and labour unions and organized representative groups (Chamber of Commerce, Federation of Austrian Industries, Association of Municipalities Carinthia, Association of Cities, Convention of Scottish Local Authorities)

It was a great success that participants from over 20 countries attended the conference. For the practice partners, getting to know each other, networking and exchanging ideas in the 'Interculturality in Practice' session was especially important. The local public administrations and local policy makers as well as regional policy makers took away suggestions for their work with regard to anchoring the topic of migration and integration as a cross-cutting issue and aim to implement further projects in the area of housing and outreach integration work: The Association of Municipalities used the conference as a hook to inform the municipalities more about the topic of demographic change and what opportunities international immigration can offer for the rural areas of Carinthia. The province of Carinthia also took up suggestions for its daily work and strive to use the potentials of rural areas in the field of refugee accommodation.

Media coverage

Photo 13 The press conference before the conference with (starting from the left): Kristijan Miksche (City of Villach), Anne Gueller-Frey (Tür an Tür), Marika Gruber (CUAS) and Jussi P. Laine (University of Eastern Finland). ©Gözde Kazaz

The conference committee organized a press conference in the morning of Day 1. The Austrian broadcaster ORF Kärnten prepared an extensive report from the conference, which was shown on television and available to watch online for 7 days. ORF Kärnten also published an article on [its website](#).

On 20 November 2022, the Austrian national television ORF featured the MATILDE project in an episode of "Heimat Fremde Heimat" (the program was available online for 7 days). The program presented migration to rural and mountain regions as a positive phenomenon, which aligns with the MATILDE's objective to highlight opportunities associated with TCN migration.

The conference was also reported on in print media. Bayerische Gemeinde Zeitung published an interview with Stefan Kordel. The interview is available at [Bayerische Gemeinde Zeitung's website](#).

Program

10 November 2022

INCLUSIVE AND ENGAGING RURAL AND MOUNTAINOUS AREAS

08:00 – 09:00 Registration

09:00 – 09:30 Welcome and greetings

Günther Albel, Mayor of the City of Villach

Claudia Pacher, Member of the University Board and Head of FH Kärnten Research,
Carinthia University of Applied Sciences

Jussi P. Laine, University of Eastern Finland & **Marika Gruber**, Carinthia University of
Applied Sciences

09:30 – 09:45 Introduction to MATILDE

Jussi P. Laine, MATILDE Project Coordinator, University of Eastern Finland

09:45 – 12:00 Place matters: Diversity of migration processes

Stefan Kordel, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg

Local transformations through migration

Spotlight on selected MATILDE case studies

Chair: **Jussi P. Laine**, University of Eastern Finland

Michele Bianchi, University of Parma / **Monica Gilli**, University of Torino / **Ayhan**

Kaya, Istanbul Bilgi University / **Anna Krasteva**, New Bulgarian University & CERMES

/ **Raúl Lardiés-Bosque**, University of Zaragoza/ **Per Olav Lund**, Innland Norway

University of Applied Sciences / **Ingrid Machold**, Federal Institute of Agricultural

Economics, Rural and Mountain Research / **Tobias Weidinger**, Friedrich-Alexander

Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg

Panel Discussion: Challenges, changes and chances of and through migration

Carolina Adler, Mountain Research Initiative & MATILDE Scientific Advisory Board /
Blandine Camus, Euromontana / **Claire Charbit**, Organisation for Economic Co-
operation and Development and (OECD) & MATILDE Scientific Advisory Board /
Susanne Felzmann, Alliance in the Alps / **Danielle Gluns**, Migration Policy Research
and Transfer Centre, University of Hildesheim / **Enrique Nieto**, European Network
for Rural Development (ENRD) / **Jimmy Nzally**, Free University Brussels
Moderation: **Ayhan Kaya**, Istanbul Bilgi University

12:00 – 13:00 Lunch

13:00 – 14:30 Social and economic challenges and chances of migration to rural areas Rural
framework conditions for social and economic inclusion of migrants

Simone Baglioni, University of Parma

MATILDE findings on social and economic impacts

Jussi P. Laine, University of Eastern Finland / **Maria Luisa Caputo**, University of
Parma/ **Birgit Aigner-Walder**, Carinthia University of Applied Sciences / **Rahel M.**
Schomaker, Carinthia University of Applied Sciences

Comments by:

Birte Nienaber, University of Luxembourg and MATILDE Scientific Advisory Board
Annelies Zoomers, Utrecht University and MATILDE Scientific Advisory Board

14:30 – 15:15 MATILDE Policy Recommendations

Chair: **Jussi P. Laine**, University of Eastern Finland

Marika Gruber & Kathrin Zupan, Carinthia University of Applied Sciences

Comments by:

Paola Alvarez, International Organization for Migration – IOM / **Matyas Szabó**, Euro-
pean Commission, DG Agriculture & Rural Development, Social sustainability

15:15 – 15:40 Coffee break

15:40 – 16:30 Interculturality in practice: Examples and findings of activating research

Alliance in the Alps, Carinthia International Center / CARITAS Bolzano, CARITAS Bulgaria & CERMES / City of Villach, Convention of Scottish Local Authorities – COSLA, Diakonie de La Tour / Europahaus Klagenfurt / Institute for Applied Research on Ageing IARA / JoMoni, Okay. Zusammen leben /PIVA – Project Group Integration of Foreigners / Support to Life / Tür an Tür / VIA Bavaria – Association for Intercultural Work & NIKO – Network Intercultural Opening of Municipalities in Bavaria

16:30 – 17:30 Policy roundtable: How can we achieve an inclusive Europe with inclusive and activating rural regions?

Paola Alvarez, International Organization for Migration – IOM / **Lorraine Cook**, COSLA/ **Marika Gruber**, Carinthia University of Applied Sciences / **Anna Krasteva**, New Bulgarian University / **Jaana Nevalainen**, Finnish Ministry of the Environment / **Jakob Ruster**, Association for Intercultural Work - VIA Bavaria & NIKO – Network Intercultural Opening of Municipalities in Bavaria / **Matyas Szabó**, European Commission, DG Agriculture & Rural Development, Social sustainability
Moderation: **Jussi P. Laine**, University of Eastern Finland

17:30 Evening reception of the City of Villach

Günther Albel, Mayor of the City of Villach

11 November 2022

THE FUTURE OF LIVING TOGETHER IN RURAL AREAS

08:00 – 09:00 Registration

09:00 – 09:30 Welcome and greetings

Hermine Bauer, interim. Head of the School of Management, Carinthia University of Applied Sciences / **Gerda Sandriesser**, Deputy Mayor and Councillor for Integration, City of Villach / **Marika Gruber**, Carinthia University of Applied Sciences

09:30 – 10:00 Current trends in population development and consequences for rural regions in Austria and Europe

Anne Goujon, Austrian Academy of Sciences

10:00 – 10:30 All those who are here are from here? Paradoxes of integration and their consequences for rural areas

Judith Kohlenberger, Vienna University for Economics and Business

10:30 – 11:00 Coffee break

11:00 –12:30 Social and economic integration processes in Carinthia and Vorarlberg

Overview of migration-related developments in Carinthia and Vorarlberg

Birgit Aigner-Walder, Carinthia University of Applied Sciences

Results from the Austrian case study regions

Marika Gruber & Jessica Pöcher Carinthia University of Applied Sciences

Ingrid Machold, Federal Institute of Agricultural Economics, Rural & Mountain Research

12:30 – 13:30 Lunch break

13:30 – 14:00 Challenges of labour market integration and social coexistence - discussion and commentary on the case study results

Gudrun Biffel, University for Continuing Education Krems

14:00 – 15:30 Views from beyond on the Austrian case study results

Stefan Kordel, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg

Raúl Lardiés-Bosque, University of Zaragoza

Panel discussion: Coexistence in rural areas – what does it take and how can this be achieved?

Eugen Hartmann, Chairman of REGIO Klostertal-Arlberg / **Gerda Sandriesser**,

Deputy Mayor and Councillor for Integration, City of Villach / **Eva Grabherr**,

Managing director of okay. zusammen leben – Projektstelle für Zuwanderung und Integration / **Mandana Poureh**, Integration Officer, Carinthian Provincial

Government

Moderation: **Kathrin Stainer-Hämmerle**, Carinthia University of Applied Sciences

Gender balance

The following tables provide information about the numbers and genders of participants, based on the registration list. On each day of the conference, about 2/3 of participants were women. Both on-site and online, the majority of participants were women. Concerning the panelists and presenters, female experts were more numerous than male. The organization committee actively monitored gender balance among invited speakers and made sure that a female expert was present as an on-site guest in every part of the program.

Day 1

	All participants	Women	Men	no information
On-site	96	62	31	3
Online	56	26	18	12
Total	152	88	49	15

Day 2

	All participants	Women	Men	no information
On-site	87	59	28	2
Online	46	31	15	11
Total	133	90	43	13

Presenters and panelists on Day 1¹

	All	Women	Men
On-site	20	11	9
Online	12	8	4
Total	32	19	13

Presenters and panelists on Day 2

	All	Women	Men
Total	15	12	3

¹ Figures are based on the program. The table does not include the participants of the Interculturality in Practice session.